

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY ON CONSUMER LOYALTY THROUGH CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (CRM)

Murti Sari Dewi¹, Muji Rahayu²

^{1,2} Management Study Program, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi STAN IM, Indonesia
Jl. Belitung No.7 Bandung

Email: 382143019@stan-im.ac.id¹, mrahayu@stan-im.ac.id²

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Abstract

This study analyzes the effect of product quality on customer loyalty through Customer Relationship Management (CRM) as a mediating variable at Company X in Cimahi City. A quantitative approach was employed using purposive sampling with 70 respondents. Data were collected through a questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale. The data were processed and analyzed using the SPSS plug-in Process Macro Hayes Model 4. The hypothesis testing results show that product quality has a positive effect on CRM, and product quality also has a positive effect on customer loyalty, although the effect is not significant. Meanwhile, CRM has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty and mediates the relationship between product quality and customer loyalty. These findings highlight the important role of CRM in strengthening the relationship between product quality and customer loyalty.

Keywords: *customer relationship management, product quality, customer loyalty.*

INTRODUCTION

The increasing intensity of competition in the business world requires companies to focus beyond simply increasing sales quickly, and instead focus on building sustainable relationships with consumers. In such conditions, consumer loyalty becomes a key asset for companies, as highly loyal consumers tend to make repeat purchases, demonstrate consistent commitment to the brand, and convey positive recommendations to others. Loyalty also provides a competitive advantage because the cost of retaining customers is relatively lower than the cost of acquiring new ones (Griffin & Lowenstein, 2002). Consumer loyalty is fundamentally driven by various factors, one of which is product quality. A product's quality is reflected in its ability to meet consumer needs and expectations, as evidenced by aspects such as its performance, reliability, durability, and conformance to predetermined specifications. A product perceived as high quality will enhance consumer perceived value, thereby boosting satisfaction and a desire to repurchase. However, not every high-quality product guarantees consumer loyalty. In practice, consumer considerations focus not solely on the product's physical quality but also on the interactive experiences they experience during their relationship with the company.

In the context of Company X in Cimahi City, maintaining customer loyalty is crucial in an increasingly competitive business environment. Companies not only need to provide high-quality products but also need to foster positive relationships with customers to create sustainable interactions. In this context, customer relationship management (CRM) is a strategy considered relevant to implement. CRM is understood as a company's strategy for building, maintaining, and developing sustainable, mutually beneficial relationships with customers through integrated information, communication, and service management (Kotler & Armstrong, 2004). Various previous studies provide evidence that CRM makes a significant contribution to increasing loyalty. Research by (Jaelani, 2020) shows that CRM variables, which include several components, namely processes and technology, have been proven to have a significant influence on customer loyalty at Bank X in Bandung City. When tested individually, human resources and process variables have a significant relationship with customer loyalty. These findings are supported by (Kalalo, 2013) who proves that effective CRM implementation has a significant effect on customer loyalty. (Adnin et al., 2013) also emphasizes that customer loyalty can be increased through intensive relationship management and consistent service. On the other hand, (Zahida et al., 2023) revealed that CRM shows a significant impact on the formation of customer loyalty, where the level of customer satisfaction functions as a mediating element in this engagement. A literature review by (Akbar et al., 2025) also shows that the effectiveness of CRM in

various contexts can increase customer loyalty, both directly and through intermediary mechanisms. However, there is still limited research examining the role of CRM as a mediator in the relationship between product quality and consumer loyalty. Most previous studies have focused on customer satisfaction or other variables as mediators. This situation indicates a research gap regarding how CRM can function as a process that bridges the impact of product quality on consumer loyalty in a more comprehensive manner. Therefore, this study is relevant to conduct to broaden understanding of the role of CRM, not only as a customer relationship strategy, but also as a mediating function that encourages the creation of a stronger relationship in the bond between product quality and consumer loyalty.

Referring to the previous explanation, this study focuses on examining how product quality contributes to increasing consumer loyalty through CRM as an intermediary variable in research at Company X in Cimahi City. The research questions posed in this study are: (1) does product quality influence consumer loyalty? (2) does product quality influence customer relationship management? (3) does customer relationship management influence consumer loyalty? and (4) does customer relationship management mediate the effect of product quality on consumer loyalty. Theoretically, the findings of this study are expected to broaden understanding in marketing management studies, particularly regarding the role of CRM in strengthening consumer loyalty. Practically, these research findings can be used as a foundation for Company X in Cimahi City in formulating strategies to increase consumer loyalty that focus not solely on product quality but also on sustainable customer relationship management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Loyalty

Consumer loyalty describes a customer's long-term commitment to continue using and supporting a product or service on an ongoing basis in the future, despite situational factors and marketing strategies employed by competitors that could potentially encourage brand switching. Loyalty is not only characterized by consumer behavior in making repeat purchases but also by the consumer's willingness to maintain a relationship with the company and provide support for the product or service used. This view is in line with the theory (Kotler & Armstrong, 2004) which emphasizes that loyalty is a form of deep customer commitment to continue purchasing and providing support for the desired product or service in the future, despite various external pressures that can influence purchasing decisions. In line with this, (Oliver, 2015:127) explains that consumer loyalty is a high level of commitment to repurchase or use services continuously on a particular product or service consistently over the long term. This commitment indicates a customer's psychological attachment to the brand, which is not easily shaken by changes in market conditions or offers from competitors. Thus, loyalty is not only behavioral, but also reflects consumer attitudes and preferences towards a brand.

Furthermore, consumer loyalty can also be understood as the level of consumer attachment and commitment to a company's brand, product, or service, demonstrated through repurchase behavior and a tendency to recommend the product to others. Loyal consumers generally have positive experiences and perceive high product value, thus being willing to become voluntary brand advocates (Christianingrum et al., 2025:72). This condition provides strategic value for companies because recommendations from loyal consumers can indirectly expand market reach. A similar view is expressed by (Darsyah et al., 2024:181) who state that the level of consumer loyalty can be seen from the customer's commitment to continue choosing the same brand or company, accompanied by a reluctance to switch to competing products or services. This loyalty is formed through repeated positive experiences, a high level of trust, and a sustained relationship between the company and the customer. Based on these various definitions, consumer loyalty in this study is understood as a form of customer commitment reflected in repeat purchasing behavior, emotional attachment to the brand, and willingness to maintain long-term relationships with the company and showing a tendency to recommend the product to other parties.

Product Quality

Product quality can be understood as a concept related to the extent to which a product is able to meet consumer standards and expectations, as reflected in its various characteristics. (Mulyadi, 2007:42) views product quality as a condition related to the conformity of product attributes to desired specifications. A product is considered high quality if its attributes do not deviate from established standards and meet the requirements for a good product. Thus, product quality also reflects the company's efforts to control and improve product attributes to ensure they remain in line with consumer needs. Furthermore, product quality is not static, but rather dynamic and can change along with the development of consumer needs and perceptions. (Pahmi, 2024:04) explains that product quality encompasses a company's strategic initiatives to meet and even exceed customer expectations, which not only focus on the product itself but also encompass elements of service, human resources, processes, and the environment. What

is considered high quality at one time can change and be considered low quality in the future, so companies are required to continue to make continuous improvements. Product quality is also often associated with a product's ability to optimally perform its primary function. (Arfah, 2022:10) states that product quality can be defined as performance quality, namely the extent to which a product can carry out its designed function consistently and free from damage. This view aligns with (Abdurachman & Arifiani, 2022:154) who emphasize that product quality indicates how well a product or service is able to meet predetermined standards and customer needs. From a marketing perspective, product quality plays a crucial role in shaping consumer perceptions and determining a product's position in the market. (Prasetyo et al., 2021:74) suggest that product quality is a key factor in marketing positioning strategies that can directly influence product or service performance in the eyes of consumers. Products with superior quality tend to be more easily accepted in the market and have stronger competitiveness. Furthermore, Kotler and Armstrong (in Ferine & Juniarti, 2022) state that product quality is a product's capacity to demonstrate its performance through various aspects such as durability, reliability, level of accuracy, and other attributes. This definition emphasizes that product quality is determined not only by the final result, but also by the ease and comfort consumers experience when using the product. A similar view is expressed by (Baroroh, 2023:34), who states that product quality encompasses the physical condition, function, and various attributes of the product, both in the form of goods and services, which are determined by quality standards that meet consumer expectations.

However, several studies indicate that product quality does not always have a direct impact on consumer loyalty. (Janita et al., 2014) in their study of McDonald's customers in MT. Haryono Malang revealed that product quality did not show a significant direct influence on consumer loyalty, although it still influenced customer satisfaction levels. This finding suggests that various factors such as performance, additional features, aesthetics, and perceived quality are not enough to drive loyalty without prior customer satisfaction. Similar findings were also found by (Santoso, 2019) on Geprek Bensu Rawamangun customers, which showed that product quality has a substantial influence on consumer commitment, even tending to be negative. This finding indicates that aspects of taste, portion, menu variety, and packaging are not enough to increase consumer loyalty, which may be more determined by other factors such as price structure, service experience, and individual tendencies. In addition to product quality, various other elements such as service quality, price level, and customer experience also play an important role in consumer loyalty. Research on Chatime customers in Lamongan revealed that service quality and price significantly contribute to customer loyalty, with price being the primary factor in consumers' decision to remain loyal. This research confirms that loyalty depends not solely on product quality but also on customer service experience and price perception. Based on these various definitions, product quality in this study is understood as a product's ability to meet specifications, perform its functions optimally, and provide value that aligns with consumer expectations through performance, reliability, durability, and other supporting attributes. Superior product quality is expected to increase consumer satisfaction and strengthen ongoing relationships between companies and customers.

Customer Relationship Management

Customer relationship management (CRM) is understood as a planned strategy utilized by organizations to build and manage customer relationships systematically and sustainably. CRM focuses on collecting, managing, and utilizing customer information across multiple touchpoints to create valuable relationships and increase customer loyalty. (Arraniri et al., 2020:101) emphasize that detailed and integrated customer information management enables companies to understand customer needs more deeply, thereby maximizing long-term customer loyalty. In line with this view, (Sinollah et al., 2025:199) state that CRM refers to the approach companies use to manage customer interactions in a targeted and systematic manner, thereby improving the quality of relationships and providing long-term value for both companies and consumers. Through CRM, companies focus not only on transactional aspects but also on developing long-term relationships that benefit both parties.

CRM is also understood as a continuous learning process about customers. (Prabawanti et al., 2019:298) explain that CRM encourages companies to continuously study customer behavior and preferences and use this information to develop products and services that meet or even exceed customer expectations. This approach places customers at the center of business strategy, enabling companies to create more personalized and tailored customer experiences. From an information systems management perspective, (McLeod & Schell, 2008:247) view CRM as managing relationships between companies and customers with the aim of providing maximum value for both parties. Relationships managed effectively through CRM enable companies to gain customer loyalty and trust, while customers benefit from higher-quality services aligned with their needs. Furthermore, studies conducted by Seliana et al. (2023) and Kartika and Wiratama, (2025) found that service quality, price perception, and customer reviews significantly impact consumer loyalty, further emphasizing the importance of customer experience in the loyalty-

building process. In this context, the aspects of service quality and pricing play a role as the main determinants that influence customers' decisions to remain loyal to a particular brand or company. Furthermore, (Astuti et al., 2023:106) state that CRM can be understood as a business approach that emphasizes managing a company's relationships with its customers to create increased company value in the eyes of customers. This strategy emphasizes the importance of maintaining long-term relationships as a strategic asset for companies in responding to increasingly competitive business competition. Technological developments also strengthen the role of CRM as a support system for customer relationship management. (Popiandi et al., 2024:04) explain that CRM can be understood as an approach or information system that enables companies to manage customer relationships at a comprehensive business level, as well as facilitate communication and marketing activities through various interaction channels. With the support of information systems, CRM enables companies to establish more effective communication and be responsive to customer needs.

However, a study by Ersi & Samuel, (2014) indicates that CRM does not always have a significant impact on customer loyalty. While CRM helps companies better understand consumer needs and behavior patterns, it is not enough to create engagement that can retain customers. Customers are more concerned with product quality, benefits, and competitors offering more appropriate value. Similar results were found in a study by Victor et al., (2015) on BCA customers in Manado, which confirmed that while CRM can increase customer satisfaction, this increase does not automatically translate into loyalty. Customer loyalty is influenced by other factors such as level of trust, overall service experience, convenience of facilities, and personal preferences over other banking options. Overall, these findings illustrate that the effectiveness of CRM in creating loyalty is strongly influenced by industry conditions, customer characteristics, and the value offered by the company. CRM can be a key factor in increasing loyalty in certain situations, but its role can be weakened if other supporting factors are not optimized. Based on these various views, CRM in this study is understood as an integrated strategy and system implemented by companies as a means to manage information, interactions, and customer relationships in a sustainable manner to produce long-term value, increase satisfaction, and strengthen consumer loyalty.

Relationship between Variables

Customer relationship management (CRM) plays a mediating role in linking product quality to consumer loyalty. Effectively managing customer relationships enables positive experiences with product quality to translate into emotional attachment and long-term consumer commitment, which can be seen in repurchase behavior and the tendency to recommend products to other consumers. Thus, CRM is a crucial mechanism in strengthening the link between product quality and ongoing customer loyalty. The mediating role of customer relationship management (CRM) in this study was tested using the Hayes Process Macro Model 4, which allows for simultaneous analysis of the direct and indirect effects between the study variables. The analysis was conducted using a bootstrapping technique to obtain a 95% confidence interval for the indirect effect, thus confirming whether CRM has a significant mediating function in linking product quality and consumer loyalty, as shown in the following study model:

Figure 1. Research Model

Based on the previously prepared research model, the relationship between variables in this study is described through the following four hypotheses:

- H₁** : Product quality has a significant positive influence on consumer loyalty.
- H₂** : Product quality has a positive and significant impact on *customer relationship management* (CRM).
- H₃** : *Customer relationship management (CRM)* has a significant positive impact on consumer loyalty.
- H₄** : *Customer relationship management (CRM)* mediates the influence of product quality on consumer loyalty.

METHOD

This study used a quantitative approach to examine how product quality influences consumer loyalty through the role of CRM as an intermediary in the relationship. The study was conducted on consumers of Company X in Cimahi City. The variables studied included product quality as the independent variable, CRM as the intermediary variable, and consumer loyalty as the dependent variable. The study sample consisted of 70 participants selected using a purposive sampling approach. Respondent selection was based on specific criteria within the context of this study, namely customers who had made at least two purchases in the last two months and were at least 17 years old. The research data were obtained through a closed-ended questionnaire instrument compiled based on indicators for each research variable. Respondents' answers were assessed using a Likert scale with a range of choices ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The data were then analyzed using SPSS through Process Macro Hayes Model 4 to analyze direct and indirect relationships between the research variables. The mediation test was conducted using the bootstrapping technique at a 95% confidence level. A mediation effect is declared significant if the confidence interval for the indirect effect does not include 0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Partial Test Results

Table 1. Partial Test Results

	Coeff	Se	t	P
Kualitas Produk	0,417	0,119	3,513	0,001

Source: data processing (2026)

Variabel dependen: Customer Relationship Management

Based on the analysis results in Table 1 regarding the effect of product quality on CRM, a coefficient value of 0.417 was found for the product quality aspect, with a t-value of 3.513 and a significance probability value (p) of 0.0001 (p < 0.05). This finding indicates a statistically significant positive effect of product quality on CRM. The coefficient of 0.417 indicates a positive relationship, meaning that increases in product quality tend to be accompanied by improved relationships between companies and customers. Thus, increased product quality will contribute to strengthening the existing relationship. These results confirm that product quality plays an important role in establishing long-term relationships between companies and consumers.

Table 2. Partial Test Results

Variabel	Coeff	Se	T	p
Kualitas Produk	0,286	0,200	1,426	0,158
Customer Relationship Management	0,994	0,189	5,270	0,000

Source: data processing (2026)

Variabel dependen: Consumer Loyalty

Next, the test results regarding the effects of product quality and CRM on consumer loyalty are presented in Table 2. The analysis revealed a coefficient for product quality as a variable of 0.286, with a t-value of 1.426 and a p-value of 0.158 (p > 0.05). Therefore, product quality was not proven to have a significant influence on consumer loyalty. Therefore, product quality alone cannot directly strengthen customer loyalty. Referring to the research findings, product quality did not show a significant direct effect on consumer loyalty. Determining consumer loyalty requires not only

product quality but also the quality of the relationships built by the company. In this regard, CRM plays a crucial role as a means for companies to build communication, provide customer attention, and create ongoing relationships that can enhance consumer loyalty. Conversely, based on the analysis results, the CRM variable showed a coefficient of 0.994, with a t-value of 5.270 and a significance level (p) of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). These results indicate that CRM has a strong and significant influence on consumer loyalty. These findings suggest that relationships that are cared for and valued, as well as a good relationship with the company, encourage consumers to demonstrate higher levels of loyalty.

Table 3. Simultaneous Test

	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
Constant	17,579	21,089	2,000	67,000	0,0000

Source: data processing (2026)

Variabel dependen: Consumer Loyalty

To complement the partial testing conducted previously, a simultaneous test (F test) was conducted to analyze the influence of product quality and customer relationship management (CRM) together in determining consumer loyalty. Based on the analysis results, the F value was recorded at 21.089 and showed a significance level (p) of 0.000 with ($p < 0.05$). Thus, product quality and CRM were proven to have a significant influence when tested simultaneously on consumer loyalty. This means that although individually product quality has not shown a significant influence, when combined with the CRM variable, both variables are simultaneously able to explain variations in consumer loyalty.

Total Effect, Direct Effect, dan Indirect Effect

Tabel 4. Total Effect

Effect	Se	T	P
0,700	0,218	3,215	0,002

Source: data processing (2026)

Tabel 5. Direct Effect

Effect	Se	T	P
0,286	0,200	1,426	0,158

Source: primary data processing (2026)

Tabel 6. Indirect Effect

Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
0,414	0,237	0,024	0,950

Source: primary data processing (2026)

Based on Table 4 and Table 5, it can be observed that product quality contributes to consumer loyalty through a total influence reaching 0.700, where the t-value is recorded at 3.215 and a significance level (p) of 0.002 ($p < 0.05$). Thus, overall product quality shows a significant and positive influence in increasing consumer loyalty. However, based on the direct effect test, product quality as a variable shows a coefficient value of 0.286 with a t-value recorded at 1.426 and a significance level (p) of 0.158 ($p > 0.05$), which means there is no evidence of a significant direct effect on consumer loyalty. Furthermore, Table 6 shows the results of the analysis regarding the indirect effect of product quality in influencing consumer loyalty channeled through the mediating role of CRM, where the value of the mediation effect (indirect effect) is 0.414 and BootSE 0.237 as well as the confidence interval of BootLLCI of 0.024 and BootULCI of 0.950. The confidence interval does not include 0, indicating that the indirect effect is significant. This finding indicates that CRM acts as a mediator, acting as a bridge between product quality and consumer loyalty. Therefore, improving product quality plays a role in strengthening consumer loyalty when supported by good customer relationship management.

CONCLUSION

The analysis revealed that product quality significantly and positively influences customer relationship management (CRM). These results indicate that improving product quality can foster better relationships between

companies and customers, thus supporting the formation of long-term relationships with consumers. However, the direct relationship between product quality and consumer loyalty did not demonstrate a sufficient level of significance. This indicates that product quality is not strong enough on its own to increase consumer loyalty without other supporting factors. On the other hand, CRM has been shown to have a significant positive impact on consumer loyalty. Furthermore, simultaneous test results indicate that product quality and CRM significantly influence consumer loyalty, suggesting that both variables play a role in fostering consumer loyalty. Furthermore, the analysis shows that CRM functions as a bridge between product quality and consumer loyalty. This means that product quality tends to have a greater impact on consumer loyalty when supported by effective customer relationship management. Therefore, CRM plays a significant role as a mediating variable in linking product quality to consumer loyalty. The research findings suggest practical implications: companies need to optimize customer relationship management through the effective use of CRM. While product quality is a crucial factor, effective CRM management in building relationships with customers can significantly enhance their role in increasing customer loyalty. Therefore, companies should focus on enhancing personalized interactions and communication with customers, ensuring that the customer experience with the company contributes to increased loyalty. Effective CRM implementation can create a more satisfying customer experience, helping companies build sustainable, mutually beneficial relationships.

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